

A Hybrid PSO and Kruskal Approach for Neutrosophic Trapezoidal Minimum Spanning Tree Problem

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Abstract. The goal of the Minimum Spanning Tree Problem (Min-STP) is to build a spanning tree (ST) in a network or graph while minimising the overall edge cost. Logistics, interaction, mobility, and scheduling are just a few of the many real-world applications of this simple combinatorial optimisation problem. However, in real-life Min-STP circumstances, uncertainty due to inconsistent, ambiguous, or missing information makes accurate estimation of edge weights difficult. The neutrosophic set is a useful tool to manage these types of problems. In this manuscript, trapezoidal neutrosophic sets are used to describe the edge weights of the neutrosophic graph. We define this problem as Neutrosophic trapezoidal Min-STP (NTMin-STP). Using trapezoidal neutrosophic sets to describe edge cost uncertainty, this paper presents a particle swarm optimisation (PSO) technique for solving NTMin-STP in a neutrosophic environment. We also modify Kruskal's technique to solve the NTMin-STP. In contrast to conventional methods, PSO provides flexibility in managing dynamic and sizable networks, which makes it especially appropriate for real-world scenarios where edge weights fluctuate. PSO's population-based search effectively explores the solution space, reducing the risk of local optima. We provide numerical examples to demonstrate the efficacy of the suggested PSO-based Min-STP technique. The findings show that PSO is a viable substitute for managing Min-STP uncertainty, providing a reliable and flexible solution.

Keywords: Neutrosophic set; Min-STP; neutrosophic network/graph; Prim's algorithm.

1. Introduction

The Min-STP is a well-known and often used constraint optimisation problem, applicable in both operations research and graph theory. There are many real-world uses for it [1–3],

such as for managing the supply chain, logistical management, computation of images, mobile internet connections, and analysis of clusters.

In an connected, weighted, undirected graph $G = (X, Y)$, X is a set of items/vertices/nodes and Y is a finite set of relationship/edges/arcs with costs, length or weight. Tree is a G with connections but no circuits. Let t denote a spanning tree (ST) of a connected graph if and only if t is a subgraph of graph G and includes all vertices of graph G . A spanning tree (ST) T is sometimes termed the biggest possible subtree inside graph G due to its possession of the maximum number of edges among all viable trees in G . The MST is a spanning tree in which the total weight of the edges is minimised.

The conventional Min-STP is defined on a graphical representation of network, whereby the nodes of the graph G indicate items, places, or entities, and the arcs illustrate the links or connections among them (e.g., highways connecting various villages). Traditional graphs require perfect knowledge of items and their interactions, making them appropriate for straightforward deterministic situations. Nevertheless, in practical implementations, this assumption often proves impractical owing to intrinsic ambiguities in characterising objects, their interrelations, or both. Consequently, the crisp graph model becomes insufficient for adequately depicting such issues.

A fuzzy set (FS) is a notion that was developed by Zadeh [4]. This idea has the potential to address the incidence of uncertainty, ambiguity, and imprecision in daily life. In the context of membership function/grade/degree, the most important attribute of an FS is a grade/function/degree that has an interval of $[0,1]$. In many different domains, the concept of FSs has been used to copy a number of different COPs. It is not possible for the FS (type-1/classical FS), whose membership grade is an actual value, to handle the many various forms of uncertainty that are present in situations that occur in the real world. While Turksen was describing the notion of FS with interval membership value, Atanassov [5] was also describing the notion of intuitionistic FSs. The notion was designed to address the issue of non membership grade of standard FSs. The use of this technique has been seen in a variety of situations, including decision making, COPs, artificial neural networks, medical analysis, and many more. Because it uses a modified variant of the traditional FS, it has the ability to take into account not only a membership grade for each element, but it also takes into account a non-membership grade with each element. More flexibility to deal with uncertainties of actual issue [6], [7], [8] is captured by it, which is a significant improvement above the basic FS's performance. Membership, non-membership, and hesitancy are the three distinct sorts of membership grades that are available for all of the items that are included in this collection. Atanassov (1989) proposed a modification to the concept of FSs, which he referred to as

interval valued intuitionistic FSs. This modification was made in order to capture a greater number of uncertainties than intuitionistic FSs.

Nevertheless, several real world problems [9] have been solved using intuitionistic FS, although these methods are unable to adequately represent many forms of uncertainty. As an example, the FS is unable to function with the uncertainties because of the indeterminate information and the contradictory information being presented. The possibility of the choice being true is 0.8, the likelihood of it being false is 0.7, and the possibilities of uncertainty are 0.5. If you are seeking the opinion of an expert on a decision, then he may say any of these things. This sort of problem that occurs in the actual world cannot be modelled with FS. In order to find a solution to this problem, innovative thinking is required.

The author of [10] came up with the concept of NS in order to provide an explanation for knowledge and facts that may be inadequate, uncertain, foggy, imprecise, ambiguous, and inconsistent in a variety of real-world circumstances. A true membership grade/degree/function, an indeterminate membership degree/grade/function, and a false membership degree/grade/function separately are the three membership grades that are used in the process of defining it. They are inside the range of values that are considered to be either nonstandard or standard unit intervals. Due to the fact that it is able to manage information that is inconsistent and incomplete in a proficient manner, NS is commonly used by researchers in order to address issues that are encountered in real-life scenarios.

The Min-STP algorithm is a well known algorithm in graph theory [7] that has the capability to ascertain the Min-STP of a graph. The traditional Min-STP has a variety of uses in reality, such as clustering, mobile communication, networks of machines, recognise voices, social media platforms, and many more. Assuming certain crisp values (actual numbers) to define the edge lengths of the graph, the conventional Min-STP is deemed to have exact edge lengths. This is because the expert thinks that the edge lengths are accurate. Nevertheless, in everyday circumstances, the duration of the edge could indicate a criterion such as time, expense, request, capacity, and so on that would not be appropriate for a fixed parameter. We may take into consideration real-life circumstances that occur in the city's road networks. The edge length, which describes the amount of time it takes for a vehicle to get from one city to another, may change depending on unpredictable circumstances such as shifting weather conditions, heavy traffic flow, or other reasons. On the other hand, the geometric distance or road distance between two cities remains constant. Dey (2016) provides a reference. Because of this, it is very perplexing for an expert to presume that an appropriate edge length in real numbers, also known as crisp values, is correctly represented. In the form of approximate intervals, linguistic phrases, and other such things, specialists could take into consideration a variety of plausible values for edge lengths. Some examples of edge durations that may be

used to describe this route of network issue are "around 30 to 50 minutes," "about 10 hour," "between 3 and 7 hours," and "nearly 3 to 6 hours," among others. The conventional FS was used by a number of scholars in order to characterise the uncertainty in edge weights. On the other hand, basic FS does not accurately represent such ambiguous or partial pieces of information since their membership grades are very clear. The concept of a neutrosophic network or graph may be thought of as a modified form of the fuzzy graph, which is specifically designed to cope with circumstances that are ambiguous.

During the last 10 years, scholars have focused an enormous amount of study on the principle of the conventional Min-STP as well as its many potential uses. The basis of the Min-STP is a graphs [11], [12], or networks. As a consequence of this, a great number of effective methods for the determination of the Min-STP solution in classical networks have been created. There are a number of sources that offer insights about Min-STP. Some of these references are [13], [14], [15], [16], and [17]. To calculate the MST of a network, professionals may only employ Prim's algorithm [14] when the edge weights or lengths are represented as real or crisp integers. This is because Prim's algorithm has been generally recognised as an effective approach for solving the MST of a crisp graph. Randomness and imprecise or incomplete information have been recognised by academics as the two key drivers of parameter uncertainty. This is due to the fact that real-world Min-STP implementations always contain a certain degree of uncertainty. For this reason, many scientists have modelled the edges or links in a Min-STP as random variables. This is despite the fact that probability theory has been used to overcome uncertainties that are caused by randomness. Following the first introduction of the Min-STP with random edge weights or costs by Ishii [18], Ishii [19] subsequently presented an efficient polynomial-time technique for resolving this issue. This technique calculates arc lengths by using confidence intervals that are obtained from stochastic data. It does this by using a number of probability distribution characteristics. However, in situations that occur in real life, these characteristics often stay unknown, and the values of these parameters display uncertainty in the form of vagueness, fuzziness, or incompleteness. The pioneering work of Itoh et al. [19] approach in the field of Min-STP research inside a fuzzy environment was accomplished by the utilisation of chance-constrained programming and requirement assessment in order to tackle the issue at hand. After that, Chang [20] published the fuzzy Min-STP, which is a method in which fuzzy arc lengths are expressed as fuzzy integers. Through the use of the ranking index approach [21], the author employed three distinct strategies in order to compare several fuzzy arc lengths. In order to further improve the approach to issue-solving, researchers have combined fuzzy set theory and probability theory. This has resulted in the creation of algorithmic approaches and a genetic algorithm that is specifically built to handle this problem. It was later that Janiak et al. [22] expanded the fuzzy spanning tree issue. They

did this by encoding arc lengths as interval fuzzy numbers and utilising ideas of possibility theory in order to compare and pick edges for the spanning tree in a fuzzy graph. While this was going on, Zhao et al. [23] investigated the use of intuitionistic fuzzy sets (FS) and integers to express edge weights. As a result, they proposed a unique algorithmic strategy for addressing this combinatorial optimisation problem (COP). Zhang et al. [24] made further contributions by offering an algorithmic way to identify the answer to the problem. They introduced the fuzzy Min-STP using hesitant fuzzy sets as fuzzy edge weights.

In recent years, some researchers have explored the Min-STP within a neutrosophic system, redefining it as the neutrosophic Min-STP (NMin-STP), which is considered to offer a more logical, reliable, and rational approach to practical applications of Min-STP. Ye [25] proposed an algorithmic approach aimed at addressing the Minimum Steiner Tree Problem (Min-STP) in a neutrosophic network or graph, wherein objects, nodes, or vertices are defined by neutrosophic sets, and the edges connecting various nodes represent the degree of dissimilarity among items. Kandasamy [26] outlined a double-valued NMin-STP and suggested a clustering algorithm for classifying data or information clusters.

Mandal and Basu [27] proposed an innovative method for addressing optimal Steiner Tree (ST) problems by integrating data that is inconsistent, inappropriate, incomplete, ambiguous, and indeterminate, utilising neutrosophic sets (NSs) to represent the arc lengths. Although neutrosophic numbers and fuzzy numbers have similarities in notation, their conceptual representations are essentially distinct. To our knowledge, no approach has been developed for solving the Minimum Spanning Tree (MST) with interval neutrosophic arc lengths, indicating a significant gap in the literature that needs additional investigation.

The Minimum Spanning Tree Problem (Min-STP) is recognised as a crucial combinatorial optimisation issue [28], [29] in operations research due to its broad applicability in real-world situations; however, the precise assessment of edge weights is a significant challenge because of the inconsistency, inappropriateness, bias, ambiguity, and indeterminacy of the information used in practical applications. Due to its esteemed capacity to effectively manage inconsistencies and uncertainties, numerous researchers contend that neutrosophic sets and logic should supplant fuzziness in uncertainty modelling, as they offer a more comprehensive approach to addressing inconsistencies, inaccuracies, incompleteness, ambiguities, and indefiniteness in data representation.

Despite the plethora of works examining the use of neutrosophic sets and their generalisations in the formulation of Min-STP models, significant chances remain for future progress in this field. The primary objective of this study is to propose an algorithmic method that effectively addresses the Min-STP in a neutrosophic network, therefore enhancing the existing understanding in this field. Recently, numerous scholars [29–31] have developed methodologies

to ascertain the Minimum Spanning Tree (MST) of a neutrosophic network or graph, utilising the fundamental Neutrosophic Set to define the MST of these networks.

This paper investigates a Min-STP where edge weights are represented as neutrosophic numbers, and a modified Kruskal’s algorithm has been developed to determine both the NMin-STP of a specified graph and its weight as a score value. The emphasis is on a neutrosophic network or graph, where edge weights are represented as neutrosophic numbers. The selection of the arc with the lowest score is prioritised, as a ranking system based on score values is established to aid the decision-making process. We also describe a PSO algorithm to design the particle swarm optimisation (PSO) technique for solving NTMin-STP in a neutrosophic environment.

2. Preliminary

Definition 2.1. Let \mathcal{UNIV} be a universal set and Y signify NS [32]. The NS Y comprises three degrees of membership. There exist true membership grade $\mathcal{TRUE}_Y(m)$, indeterminate membership grade $\mathcal{IND}_Y(m)$, and false membership grade $\mathcal{FAL}_Y(m)$, respectively.

$$-0 \leq \sup \mathcal{TRUE}_Y(m) + \sup \mathcal{IND}_Y(m) + \sup \mathcal{FAL}_Y(m) \leq 3^+ \tag{1}$$

Definition 2.2. The single-valued NS [?] R on \mathcal{UNIV} is shown as follows.

$$A = \{ \langle k : \mathcal{TRUE}_Y(m), \mathcal{IND}_Y(m), \mathcal{FAL}_Y(m) | k \in \mathcal{U} \rangle \} \tag{2}$$

The true value $\mathcal{TRUE}_Y(m)$ belongs to the $[0, 1]$, the indeterminate membership grade $\mathcal{IND}_r(m)$ is confined to the range $[0, 1]$, and the false membership grade $\mathcal{FAL}_A(m)$ also exists within the interval $[0, 1]$, fulfilling the subsequent condition:

$$-0 \leq \sup \mathcal{TRUE}_Y(m) + \sup \mathcal{IND}_Y(m) + \sup \mathcal{FAL}_Y(m) \leq 3^+ \tag{3}$$

Definition 2.3. Let \tilde{D} describes a single valued trapezoidal neutrosophic number (SVTNN) [33] where $\tilde{D} = \langle (d_r, d_l, d_p, d_s); w_{\tilde{D}}, u_{\tilde{D}}, y_{\tilde{D}} \rangle$. The membership values can be calculated as follows

$$\mu_{\tilde{D}}(q) = \begin{cases} \frac{(q-d_r)w_{\tilde{D}}}{(d_l-d_r)} & (d_r \leq q < d_l) \\ w_{\tilde{D}} & (d_l \leq q \leq d_p) \\ \frac{(d_s-p)w_{\tilde{D}}}{(d_s-d_p)} & (d_p < p \leq d_s) \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$v_{\tilde{D}}(q) = \begin{cases} \frac{(d_l-p+u_{\tilde{D}}(q-d_r))}{(d_l-d_r)} & (d_r \leq x < d_l) \\ u_{\tilde{D}} & (d_l \leq q \leq d_p) \\ \frac{(q-d_p+u_{\tilde{D}}(d_s-p))}{(d_s-d_p)} & (d_p < x \leq d_s) \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

and

$$\lambda_{\tilde{D}}(q) = \begin{cases} \frac{(d_l - p + y_{\tilde{D}}(q - d_r))}{(d_l - d_r)} & (d_r \leq q < d_l) \\ y_{\tilde{D}} & (d_l \leq q \leq d_p) \\ \frac{(x - d_p + y_{\tilde{D}}(d_s - p))}{(d_s - d_p)} & (d_p < p \leq d_s) \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

respectively.

Definition 2.4. Let \tilde{D} is a single valued triangular neutrosophic number (SVTrN-number) [33] where $\tilde{D} = \langle (d_r, d_l, d_p,); w_{\tilde{D}}, u_{\tilde{D}}, y_{\tilde{D}} \rangle$. We can calculate membership values in the following manner:

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_{\tilde{D}}(q) &= \begin{cases} \frac{(q - d_r)w_{\tilde{D}}}{(d_l - d_r)}, & (d_r \leq q < d_l) \\ \frac{(d_p - p)w_{\tilde{D}}}{(d_p - d_l)}, & (d_l \leq q < d_p) \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \\ v_{\tilde{D}}(q) &= \begin{cases} \frac{(d_l - p + u_{\tilde{D}}(q - d_r))}{(d_l - d_r)}, & (d_r \leq q < d_l) \\ \frac{(q - d_l + u_{\tilde{D}}(d_p - p))}{(d_p - d_l)}, & (d_l \leq q \leq d_p) \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \\ \lambda_{\tilde{D}}(q) &= \begin{cases} \frac{(d_l - p + y_{\tilde{D}}(q - d_r))}{(d_l - d_r)}, & (d_r \leq q < d_l) \\ \frac{(q - d_l + y_{\tilde{D}}(d_p - p))}{(d_p - d_l)}, & (d_l \leq x \leq d_p) \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

If $d_r \geq 0$ and at least $c > 0$ then $\tilde{D} = \langle (d_r, d_l, d_p, d_s); w_{\tilde{D}}, u_{\tilde{D}}, y_{\tilde{D}} \rangle$ it is affirmed to be positive SVTrN-number, denoted by $\tilde{D} > 0$. Let $\tilde{D} = \langle (d_{r1}, d_{l1}, d_{p1}, d_{s1}); w_{\tilde{D}}, u_{\tilde{D}}, y_{\tilde{D}} \rangle$ and $\tilde{B} = \langle (d_{r2}, d_{l2}, d_{p2}, d_{s2}); w_{\tilde{D}}, u_{\tilde{D}}, y_{\tilde{D}} \rangle$ be two SVTrN-number and $d_s \neq 0$ be any real number. Then, the addition operation between \tilde{D} and \tilde{B}

$$\tilde{D} + \tilde{B} = \langle (d_{r1} + d_{r2}, d_{l1} + d_{l2}, d_{p1} + d_{p2}, d_{s1} + d_{s2}); w_{\tilde{D}} \wedge w_{\tilde{B}}, u_{\tilde{D}} \vee u_{\tilde{B}}, y_{\tilde{D}} \vee y_{\tilde{B}} \rangle \quad (4)$$

Definition 2.5. The score functions is defined as follows:

$$s(\tilde{D}) = \frac{1}{12} (d_{r1} + d_{r2} + d_{r3} + d_{r4}) * (2 + w_{\tilde{D}} - u_{\tilde{D}} - y_{\tilde{D}}) \quad (5)$$

Definition 2.6. Let D_1 and D_2 are two SVNs [34]. Then

$D_1 \succ D_2$ if and only if $s(D_1) > s(D_2)$.

$D_1 \prec D_2$ if and only if $s(D_1) < s(D_2)$.

$D_1 \sim D_2$ if and only if $s(D_1) = s(D_2)$.

Here, $D_1 \succ D_2$ expresses that the cost of the arc/edge represented by D_1 is larger than the cost of the arc/edge represented by D_2 . Similarly, $D_1 \prec D_2$ expresses that the cost of the edge described by D_1 is lower than the cost of the arc/edge described by D_2 . $D_1 \sim D_2$ expresses that the cost of the edge presented by D_1 is equal to the cost of the arc/edge described by D_2 .

3. Neutrosophic Minimal Spanning Tree (NMin-STP)

A connected, acyclic, and maximal subgraph in ST that includes all the nodes in a connected graph G . For any graph G , there are exactly $n - 1$ arcs in each ST, where n is the number of nodes. Find a ST whose arcs have the shortest possible total length; this is called a Min-STP. The authentic Min-STP considers the exact weights associated with the graph's arcs. Nevertheless, the arc lengths may not be precise since there is a lack of or inadequate data in real-world contexts. When dealing with such imprecision, neutrosophic graphs are the way to go.

3.1. Problem formulation for NMin-STP

Assume that G is a neutrosophic graph or network and G comprises p vertices $I = \{i_1, i_2, \dots, i_k\}$ and n arcs $B \subseteq I \times I$. Each edge of G is represented by p , defined as a pair of vertices (c, d) , where $c, d \in I$ and $c \neq d$. If edge n exists in the NMin-STP, then $z_e = 1$; otherwise, $z_e = 0$. The NMin-STP is articulated as the following linear programming problem.

Objective: Minimise the overall weight of the spanning tree.

Decision Variables: Let $z_{j,k}$ be a binary variable defined as:

$$z_{j,k} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if the edge } (i, j) \text{ is included in the spanning tree} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \tag{6}$$

Mathematical Formulation:

Minimize:

$$\sum_{(j,k) \in E} w_{j,k} z_{j,k} \tag{7}$$

where $w_{j,k}$ is the weight of edge (i, j) and E is the set of all edges.

Subject to:

1. **Connectivity constraint:** Ensure that the selected edges form a spanning tree with $|V| - 1$ edges:

$$\sum_{(j,k) \in E} z_{j,k} = |V| - 1 \tag{8}$$

2. **No cycles (Subtour elimination):** For any subset $S \subset V$, the number of edges within S must be less than $|S| - 1$:

$$\sum_{i,j \in S, i \neq j} z_{j,k} \leq |S| - 1, \quad \forall S \subset V, |S| \geq 2 \tag{9}$$

3. **Binary constraint on decision variables:**

$$z_{j,k} \in \{0, 1\}, \quad \forall (j, k) \in E \tag{10}$$

4. Proposed Algorithm for the NMin-STP and its cost

Our proposed neutrosophic Kruskal's algorithm is presented in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1 Algorithm of the modified neutrosophic Kruskal's algorithm for NMin-STP.

Input: An undirected connected weighted neutrosophic network/graph $H = (V, E)$ with neutrosophic edge weight.

Output: NMST $\tilde{T} = (V_t, E_t)$ of H and its cost.

```

1:  $V_t \leftarrow V$ ;                                     ▷ Initialize  $V_t$  with all vertices
2:  $E_t \leftarrow \emptyset$ ;
3: Sort all edges in  $E$  in ascending order based on their score values using (7);
4:  $C_{\tilde{T}} \leftarrow 0$ ;
5: for each edge  $(a, b) \in E$  in sorted order do
6:   if  $(a, b)$  does not form a cycle in  $E_t$  then
7:      $E_t \leftarrow E_t \cup (a, b)$ ;
8:      $C_{\tilde{T}} \leftarrow C_{\tilde{T}} \oplus \text{Score}(a, b)$ ;
9:   end if
10:  if  $|E_t| = |V| - 1$  then
11:    Break;
12:  end if
13: end for

```

5. Numerical illustrations

For purposes of illustration, we provide an example of the NMin-STP in the next part. A neutrosophic graph characterised by undirected links, valued edges, and a neutrosophic cost, represented as $G = (X, Y)$, where the neutrosophic edge weight is taken into account. This neutrosophic graph includes nine arcs and six nodes. The method we have suggested may resolve the NMin-STP and identifies the NMST of a neutrosophic network/graph, where the arc lengths are represented by trapezoidal neutrosophic sets/numbers. The eight trapezoidal neutrosophic numbers, as shown in [35], are regarded as edge weights of the neutrosophic network/graph. The trapezoidal neutrosophic numbers assigned to the arcs in this graph, seen in Figure 1, are randomly designated as arc lengths.

- i) **Step 1.** Arrange all the edges of the graph in ascending order based on their weights by using a ranking method to ascertain the numerical values corresponding to each edge. The edge with the least weight is prioritized first. Assume the smallest edge is $(1, 2)$; hence, it is included in the Minimum Spanning Tree (MST). The present edge set is $Y_n = \{(1, 2)\}$, and the linked component set is $z_n = \{1, 2\}$.

Algorithm 2 PSO_MST(Graph G , integer num_particles, integer max_iterations)

```

1: Input: Graph  $G(V, E)$  with weighted edges, number of particles (swarm size), maximum
   iterations (termination criterion)
2: Output: Optimal NMST identified

3: Step 1: Initialize particles
4: for each particle  $i$  in the swarm do
5:   Randomly construct a valid spanning tree (candidate for MST)
6:   Assign initial velocity  $V_i = 0$ 
7:   Compute fitness (sum of edge weights)
8:   Set personal best  $pBest_i$  as initial solution
9: end for

10: Step 2: Identify the optimal global solution
11: Assign  $gBest$  as the minimum cost MST among all  $pBest_i$ 

12: Step 3: Execute iterations of PSO updates
13: for iteration = 1 to max_iterations do
14:   for each particle  $i$  in the swarm do
15:     Update velocity:
16:      $V_i = w \cdot V_i + c_1 \cdot \text{rand}() \cdot (pBest_i - z_i) + c_2 \cdot \text{rand}() \cdot (gBest - z_i)$ 
17:     Apply velocity to modify the particle's tree structure
18:     Verify spanning tree validity (repair mechanism if necessary)
19:     Compute new fitness (sum of edge weights)
20:   end for

21:   Step 4: Revise individual and collective optimal values
22:   for each particle  $i$  in the swarm do
23:     if new fitness <  $pBest_i$  fitness then
24:       Update  $pBest_i$  to new solution
25:     end if
26:     if new fitness < global best fitness then
27:       Update  $gBest$  to new solution
28:     end if
29:   end for
30: end for

31: Step 5: Return the optimal Minimum Spanning Tree
32: Return  $gBest$ 

```

FIGURE 1. A neutrosophic network/graph

- ii) **Step 2.** Choose the subsequent smallest edge that does not create a cycle. Assuming that among the remaining edges, (1,5) is the next smallest. The addition to the MST results in the update of $Y_n = \{(1,2), (1,5)\}$ and the associated components as $z_n = \{1, 2, 5\}$.
- iii) **Step 3.** Select the subsequent smallest edge that does not create a cycle. The procedure is repeated until all vertices are included inside a singular spanning tree. Assuming the final selected edges are (5,6), (2,3), and (4,5), the resulting Minimum Spanning Tree (MST) comprises the edges $Y_n = \{(1,2), (1,5), (5,6), (2,3), (4,5)\}$ and the connected components are $z_n = \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, D\}$.

The Particle Swarm Optimisation (PSO) method for identifying the Minimum Spanning Tree (MST) was applied to the specified neutrosophic graph. The method was ran with several parameter configurations to evaluate its efficacy in discovering the best Minimum Spanning Tree (MST).

5.1. Experimental Configuration

The PSO algorithm was implemented on the graph $G(V, E)$ using the following parameter values: Number of particles (swarm size): $N = 30$ Maximum iterations: $T = 100$ Inertia weight: $w = 0.7$ object Cognitive coefficient: $c_1 = 1.5$ article Social coefficient: $c_2 = 1.5$

Each particle in the swarm was initialised with a randomly generated spanning tree, guaranteeing proper connection across all vertices. The fitness of each particle was calculated as the cumulative weight of its spanning tree. The optimisation procedure was executed through many iterations to reduce the MST cost.

The efficacy of the PSO-based MST methodology was evaluated based on the following criteria: Convergence Rate: The decrease in the overall Minimum Spanning Tree (MST) cost

over iterations. Computational efficiency: The time necessary to achieve the ideal Minimum Spanning Tree (MST). Item Accuracy: Validation of optimality by comparison with Kruskal’s method.

The algorithm’s convergence was noted to be consistent, exhibiting a fast reduction in the MST cost during the early iterations, thereafter stabilising as the global best solution (*gBest*) neared optimality. The ultimate MST cost achieved using PSO nearly matched the outcome produced by Kruskal’s algorithm, validating the efficacy of the method.

The ideal minimum spanning tree derived via particle swarm optimisation has the following edges: $Y_n = (1, 2), (1, 5), (5, 6), (2, 3), (4, 5)$ with a cumulative weight of $C_{MST} = 23.5$ (assuming numerical edge weights). The outcome aligns with traditional MST methods, illustrating the relevance of PSO in addressing combinatorial optimisation issues such as MST.

A LPP model is also considered to solve NMin-STP. To find the solution, LINGO software is employed. We describe our obtained result in Table 2 which is determined by software LINGO. We use a variable $z_{i,j} = 1$, if any edge i, j is in the MST. Table 2 also provides a description of the Kruskal’s algorithm solution. We get an identical solution of LINGO and our proposed algorithm.

TABLE 1. Result of NMin-STP

LINGO Solution	Kruskal’s Algorithm Solution
Min $Y = 75.06$	Cost = 75.06
$z_{23} = 1, z_{12} = 1, z_{56} = 1$	Min-STP = (23)(12)(51)(45)(56)
$z_{15} = 1, z_{45} = 1$	

6. Conclusion

In this work, we use trapezoidal neutrosophic sets to express edge weights in order to solve the Minimum Spanning Tree Problem (Min-STP) under uncertainty. We present the Neutrosophic Trapezoidal Min-STP (NTMin-STP) and offer a particle swarm optimisation (PSO) method, in conjunction with a modified Kruskal’s algorithm, to address the issue efficiently. The use of PSO provides adaptability in managing dynamic and extensive networks, showcasing its viability as a strong substitute for conventional techniques. We demonstrate the efficacy and applicability of our method in uncertain contexts with numerical examples. The suggested technique is feasible and relevant in actual fields such as supply chain management, routing, and mobility planning. Future study will aim to expand our methodology to include more sources of uncertainty beyond geometric distance, such as fluctuating trip times affected by environmental variables like weather conditions.

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